

Towards a Net Zero Emission Pathway: A CLEWs-based Study of Ghana

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Executive Summary

Ghana faces chronic energy insecurity, with 35% of national greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions originating mainly from thermal power sources. This study employs Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) modelling to evaluate three energy transition pathways through 2055: Baseline (BAU), Emission Reduction (EMR), and Nuclear Energy Addition (NUC). Results reveal that nuclear energy provides the most cost-effective decarbonization pathway at \$51.49 billion, achieving substantial emission reductions by reducing reliance on biofuel and natural gas baseload generation. Conversely, the renewable-heavy EMR scenario, targeting 20.4% natural gas and biofuel emission reduction by 2030, a contribution to the overall 64 Mt CO₂eq of Ghana's emission, costs \$97.95 billion, approximately 90% more than the nuclear pathway, due to extensive solar infrastructure, storage, and grid requirements. Both decarbonization scenarios decrease biofuel generation, with EMR achieving a 100 % reduction and NUC reducing biofuel generation by 12.6 %. The model's findings challenge conventional assumptions about the cost- and emission-effectiveness of renewable energy and suggest that nuclear power warrants serious consideration in Ghana's sustainable energy strategy, contingent on timely regulatory framework development and international partnerships. The study recommends future works to evaluate employment shifts, energy access disparities, and community impacts across various decarbonization pathways; analyse sustainable biofuel production limits in relation to land competition, deforestation risks, and food security implications; and incorporate the effects of climate change on water availability, including droughts, floods and rainfall variability, alongside its influence on agricultural productivity and power generation.

Keywords: CLEWs; Emissions; Energy Transition; Ghana; Net-Zero; Sustainability

Introduction

Climate change mitigation has emerged as a vital global priority, with nations, including Ghana, committing to significant reductions in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to limit global warming to 1.5°C (IPCC, 2018). As a developing country, Ghana faces pressures to transition to low-carbon energy systems while tackling energy access challenges. With a population of around 35 million and an electricity generation capacity of 5,454 MW (Energy Commission of Ghana, 2023), Ghana's energy landscape has evolved from predominantly hydroelectric sources to a mix that includes thermal plants and solar power. However, this diversification has increased the power sector's carbon intensity, with natural gas accounting for approximately 35% of GHG emissions (Ghana National Energy Transition Framework, 2022).

Objective

The main aim of the research was to determine the consequent impacts of Ghana's energy transition pathway on the interlinkages of energy generation, land use and water use.

Research Questions

1. What are the effects of reducing emissions from power plants on Ghana's current power generation mix, water use and land use?
2. Is the introduction of nuclear energy a feasible source of energy in Ghana's energy production mix?
3. What is the financial outlook of emission reduction and nuclear introduction into the power mix?

Methodology

This study used the Open-Source Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) modelling tool, integrating the Climate, Land, Energy and Water System (CLEWS) framework for Ghana. OSeMOSYS determines the most cost-effective approach, focusing on minimising discounted system costs (Plazas-Niño, 2024). The CLEWs Framework is grounded in modelling dynamic interactions among interdependent systems (Khaleghian et al., 2025).

The methodology follows three steps:

- I. Identification of technologies, interconnections, and data inputs
- II. Development of subsystem models for energy, water, and industry within an optimisation framework
- III. Scenario analysis to assess impacts on energy, water, employment, and emissions

Data Sources

Energy data was obtained from the International Energy Agency, Ministry of Energy and the Energy Commission; Water use data was obtained from the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), FAO Aquastat, the FAO global information system on water resources and agricultural water management. Land Data was obtained from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Population and GDP growth data were obtained from STATISTA.

Clews Reference System

Ghana's reference CLEWs system is modelled on five main energy sources (Natural Gas, Light Fuel Oil, Hydro, Solar and Biomass) for the energy system; for the Land

system, the key crops of interest included Maize, Cocoa, Oil Palm Fruit and all other crops, and the Water system being mainly rainfall, ground water and surface runoff.

Key interlinkages considered in the model include Water–Land (agriculture and irrigation), Land–Energy (bioenergy demand), Energy–Climate and Energy–Water (cooling and pumping) as depicted in Figure 2 (Khaleghian et al., 2025).

Fig 2. Ghana CLEWS Reference Model

Assumptions

Key assumptions underpinning the model include:

1. Energy demand grows consistently through 2055, regardless of the generation mix
2. Hydropower capacity remains relatively fixed due to geographical/environmental constraints
3. Existing power plants can be maintained and operated through the modelling period
4. Grid infrastructure can accommodate a changing generation mix
5. Technological advancement assumes gradual improvements in energy efficiency and renewable technologies.

Scenarios

The scenarios and sensitivity analysis for the study can be found in Table 1

Table 1: Scenarios and Sensitivity Analysis

SN	Scenario	Sensitivity Analysis
1	Baseline (BAU)	Energy Mix/Generation Emissions Investment Costs
2	Impact of Emission Reduction (EMR) Cap Gas and Bio baseline-related emissions by 20.4% by 2030 to meet a 64 Mt CO ₂ eq reduction in total emissions by 2030	
3	Introduction of 1 GW of Nuclear in 2030 (NUC)	

Results and Discussion

Baseline (BAU) vs Emission Reduction (EMR) vs Nuclear Generation (NUC) Scenarios

Energy Mix

The energy mix in the baseline (BAU) scenario consists of biomass/waste (41.4 %), hydropower (23.0 %), natural gas (35.6 %), and solar (0.02 %) technologies supplying energy demand across domestic, industrial, and transport sectors (Fig. 1). Emissions in the BAU scenario are dominated by biofuel consumption, followed by natural gas, and diesel in the agriculture sector, reaching approximately 48 Mt CO₂eq by 2055. Elevated biofuel emissions are primarily driven by increasing transport demand assumptions embedded in the baseline scenario.

In the emission-reduction (EMR) scenario, bioenergy generation is completely displaced from the mix as the optimisation framework prioritises lower-emission technologies to satisfy set system constraints. Under the nuclear (NUC) scenario, the introduction of 1 GW nuclear energy capacity from 2030 alters the generation trends relative to the baseline, by increasing solar by 28.5 % and natural gas by 12.8 %, reflecting the model's cost-emission trade-offs. Specifically, biofuel technologies exhibit a higher input-activity-ratio (2.86) compared to natural gas (2.08) or hydropower (1), meaning that more biomass is needed to produce the same quantity of energy. Hence, the lower conversion

efficiency and higher emissions intensity of bioenergy reduce its competitiveness under optimisation.

Figure 1: Projected energy mix of the (a) baseline (b) energy reduction (c) nuclear energy addition scenarios.

The Baseline (BAU) scenario primarily relies on natural gas and biofuel as the main baseload provider while integrating stable hydro and moderate solar growth contributions. This fossil-heavy mix continues to exist in the energy policies, resulting in predictable but emissions-intensive generation patterns.

The Emission Reduction (EMR) pathway, on the other hand, takes a more aggressive approach by eliminating biofuels and constraining natural gas growth in alignment with a 20.4% emission cap. This shift prioritises solar energy as the primary technology for expansion, necessitating significant investment in solar capacity, energy storage, and grid enhancement to manage intermittency, while hydro power continues at its maximum sustainable capacity.

Conversely, the Nuclear (NUC) pathway introduces clean baseload capacity through the integration of 11.5 % nuclear energy, displacing bioenergy (12.6 %), increasing natural gas (0.23 %) and hydropower (0.89 %), while solar remains the same, highlighting nuclear's effectiveness in providing reliable power.

Emissions

In terms of emission-reduction performance, the analysis reveals notable sectoral emission patterns across the three scenarios, particularly with agricultural diesel emissions, which remain unchanged in all pathways, underscoring the limitations of focusing solely on power sector decarbonization.

Following the implementation of emission constraints in the emission-reduction (EMR) scenario, the energy mix shifts substantially between 2020 and 2025. Biofuel generation, which accounted for an average of 60 % in the baseline scenario, is eliminated from the system. Natural gas generation increases from an average share of 39 % in the BAU scenario mix to more than 99 % of the energy mix, maintaining a stable trend after 2030. This indicates its role as a transitional or balancing technology under emissions limitations (Fig. 2). Solar energy generation also increases in the mix to meet energy demand while complying with the emissions cap. As a result, total emissions are significantly reduced compared to BAU, remaining at a maximum level of approximately 9 Mt CO₂eq between 2030 and 2055.

With the introduction of nuclear energy into the system, further changes in technology deployment are observed. Nuclear generation reduces both the total quantity and growth rate of biofuel-based generation through to 2055, reflecting technology substitution driven by lower emissions intensity and improved system efficiency.

Figure 2: Projected emissions trends for the baseline (a), energy reduction (b) and nuclear energy addition (c) scenarios

Natural gas mining emissions exhibit significant differentiation: the BAU shows a strong upward trend due to gas expansion, whereas the EMR pathway flattens emissions, and the NUC pathway results in substantial reductions as nuclear displaces gas generation. In sum, the EMR pathway achieves greater emission reductions by fully eliminating both biofuel and light fuel oil and actively reducing natural gas emissions, while the NUC pathway relies on fuel switching and constraints for moderate reductions. The stable agricultural emissions across all scenarios highlight the necessity for complementary strategies beyond electricity generation to realise comprehensive economy-wide decarbonization.

Investment Costs

The subtotal investment cost for the nuclear energy addition (NUC) scenario (\$51.49B) is lower than in both the baseline (BAU) scenario (\$53.96B) and the emission-reduction (EMR) scenario (\$97.95B), as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Projected investment cost for the baseline (a), energy-reduction (b) and nuclear energy addition (c) scenarios

The investment analysis presents a surprising revelation in the renewable energy landscape, identifying nuclear energy as the most cost-effective pathway for emissions reduction, contrary to common assumptions that favour renewable sources. The cost for nuclear energy is estimated at \$51.49 billion, which is 4.6% below the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. This can be attributed to several factors, including the elimination of biofuel infrastructure, reductions in natural gas investment, and minimised supplementary solar deployment.

Nuclear's economies of scale and its capacity to provide baseload energy without the need for storage contribute to its long-term financial attractiveness, especially given its operational lifespan of about 50 years. In stark contrast, the renewable-heavy emission reduction (EMR) strategy incurs a staggering cost of \$97.95 billion, reflecting an 81% increase over the BAU scenario and 90% above the nuclear option. This substantial financial requirement may be due to the extensive solar infrastructure needed to meet emission targets, coupled with the capital-intensive demands for energy storage, transmission upgrades, and backup generation to manage the intermittency of renewable sources.

The findings challenge the assumption that renewable energy pathways are always cheaper than nuclear options, particularly for Ghana, where nuclear energy delivers superior cost-effectiveness and deeper emission reductions, creating a rare win-win

scenario. In contrast, the EMR's renewable-heavy approach faces significant economic challenges while achieving only moderate decarbonization. Additionally, persistent agricultural emissions highlight the need for integrated cross-sectoral climate policies beyond just power generation. This makes the development of a nuclear regulatory framework economically justified, rather than purely environmentally motivated.

Conclusion

1. Emission reduction target is feasible with an additional investment of \$30 B more than baseline while optimising the energy mix.
2. Nuclear energy introduction significantly reduced emissions and is \$2.5B cheaper than the baseline of \$53.96B, while optimally dropping light fuel oil imports
3. Water demand remains stable across all scenarios, indicating that emission reduction strategies and nuclear adoption can be pursued without placing additional strain on Ghana's water resources.
4. Agricultural diesel remains a persistent emission source across all scenarios, highlighting the need for complementary policies targeting the agricultural sector.
5. Ghana can achieve net-zero pathways through either incremental optimisation (EMR) or transformative technology adoption (Nuclear), depending on investment capacity and policy priorities.

Recommendations

Policy Insights

1. Emissions reduction-related high capital cost requires diversified financing mechanisms from public-private partnerships, international climate finance, and development bank support.
2. The Nuclear Regulatory Authority must develop a roadmap for the immediate deployment of Nuclear Energy into Ghana's energy generation mix by 2030.
3. Integrate agricultural decarbonization into national climate strategy, implement equipment electrification programs, renewable fuel incentives, and mechanisation upgrades to achieve comprehensive emission reductions.

Future studies may:

1. Evaluate the employment shifts, energy access disparities, and community impacts across different decarbonization pathways.
2. Analyse sustainable biofuel production limits considering land competition, deforestation risks, and food security implications.
3. Incorporate climate change impacts on water availability (droughts, rainfall variability), agricultural productivity and power generation.

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